

On the Oxidising Enzymes in Betel Leaves (*Piper Betel*).

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Oxidation and oxidising enzymes play a very important rôle in the plant and animal kingdom and it is not surprising, therefore, that a large amount of experimental work and theoretical discussion have centred round the process of biological oxidation. In the 19th century we come across the theories of M. Traube, Engler, Paldin and Bach on oxidation. At present a great controversy is going on between Warburg ("Katalytische Wirkungen der lebendigen Substanz", Berlin, 1928) and Wieland (Oppenheimer, "Handbuch der Biochemie", 1925, Vol. 2, pp. 252-72) about the mechanism of biological oxidation. Warburg maintains that biological oxidation is due in all cases to an activation of oxygen brought about by the respiratory ferment which contains iron and which is like hämin in its constitution. Hydrocyanic acid inhibits biological oxidation because according to Warburg it combines with and inactivates the iron of the respiratory ferment.

Wieland on the other hand holds that the action of the oxidising enzymes, dehydrogenase as he calls them, consists in activating the hydrogen of the oxidisable substance (called donator) and this hydrogen of the donator combines with a suitable substance present in most cases and this latter substance is oxygen (called the acceptor). The primary product formed is hydrogen peroxide which is at once decomposed by the ferment catalase which is present in all cells. The inhibiting action of hydrocyanic acid is according to Wieland due to its retarding effect on catalase. That oxygen can be replaced by other suitable acceptors has been shown by Thumberg (*Arch. Physiol.*, 1921, **182**, 601; *Scand. Arch. Pysiol.*, 1928, **54**, 6) who has experimentally demonstrated that in biological oxidations methylene blue can very well replace oxygen.

Recently Keilin (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1929, **B**, **104**, 206, 250) by his work on the cytochrome of the cell has tried to co-ordinate the theories of Wieland and Warburg; according to Keilin the main

respiratory system of the cell comprises the following components: (a) dehydrogenase, (b) metabolites, (c) cytochrome, (d) molecular oxygen.

It is clear that investigation of oxidising systems in varied and simple systems will ultimately enable us to gain an insight into the nature of oxidising enzymes and the mechanism of oxidation.

An investigation of the oxidising enzymes in betel leaves which are so common in India was therefore taken up.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Betel leaves were washed thoroughly under tap water and finally with distilled water so as to free from adhering foreign matters. Then they were cut into small pieces and rubbed in an iron mortar. The juice was then pressed out of the mass by means of a pressing machine. It was then kept in a clean sterile vessel and was centrifuged for about 30 minutes. The juice was then ready for experiments. It was found to be acidic and was neutralised exactly with caustic soda solution ($N/2$). It was then brought to desired p_H value by adding necessary amounts of acid or alkali using Clark and Lubb's series of indicators. 5 C.c. of juice of any suitable p_H of the solution was kept at constant p_H with $M/10$ -phosphate buffer. Thus the reaction mixture contained 10 c.c. substrate solution, 5 c.c. betel leaf juice, 2 c.c. buffer and 1 c.c. water in a Barcroft-Warburg respirometer. The same sample of betel juice was used for experiments with the same substrate which was carried out simultaneously.

Apparatus.—The apparatus that was set up for oxidation measurements was a series of 8 Barcroft-Warburg respirometers which could be moved in a thermostat. The fall of pressures with the absorption of oxygen was indicated by the manometers, which were filled up with Brodie's solution.

Each vessel was provided with a reservoir containing caustic potash solution to absorb carbon dioxide.

A knowledge of the volume of the vessels is necessary to find out the volume of oxygen absorbed from the noted difference. The constant K of the vessel is calculated according to the following formula of Warburg.

$$K = \frac{\frac{273}{T} V_a + V_r \alpha}{P_0}$$

Where V_o is the volume of the vessel, V_r that of the liquid in the vessel, T the absolute temperature, P_o , the normal pressure (10,000 mm. Brodie) and a , the absorption coefficient of the gas that disappears. The volume V of oxygen that is used up in oxidation is given by $Kh = V$, where h is the difference of pressure registered by the manometer.

One Barcroft vessel contained only water of the same volume as in other vessels to correct for the changes in temperature. Another vessel contained only betel juice at the desired p_H with buffer to find out the amount of oxygen, if any, absorbed by the juice itself. In both cases the correction necessary was found to be very small and always taken into account.

Action of the betel juice on different substrates *e.g.* hydroquinone, leucine, succinic acid, acetaldehyde, linoleic acid and oleic acid was tried. The temperatures employed were 34.4° and 25° . A stock solution of each substance was prepared and 10 c.c. of this substrate solution brought to the desired p_H before each experiment. As already indicated the total volume of reaction mixture was 18 c.c.

It must be made clear at the outset that the oxidising capacity of different samples of juice was different, the limits of variation being about 50%. The experiments with each substrate, however, were carried out with one and the same sample, and at the same time. The following tables indicate the results.

The following abbreviations have been used in the tables: t = time in min., P_d = pressure difference in cm., K = vessel constant and V_o = volume of oxygen absorbed in c.c.

TABLE I a.

Hydroquinone.

 Temp. = 25° . Strength of stock solution = 2%.

t_s	p_H 4.49 $K = 0.0057$		p_H 5.2 $K = 0.0051$		p_H 6.2 $K = 0.0049$		p_H 6.8 $K = 0.0061$	
	$P_d.$	$V_o.$	$P_d.$	$V_o.$	$P_d.$	$V_o.$	$P_d.$	$V_o.$
10	4.4	0.02508	5.8	0.02958	5.6	0.02744	4.5	0.02745
35	18.6	0.10402	22.4	0.11424	20.8	0.10192	15.1	0.09211
60	35.3	0.20121	37.6	0.19176	35.4	0.17346	25.1	0.15917

TABLE I b.

Temp. = 34.4°.

t.	p_H 4.49 $K=0.0055$		p_H 5.2 $K=0.005$		p_H 6.2 $K=0.0048$	
	$P_d.$	$V_o.$	$P_d.$	$V_o.$	$P_d.$	$V_o.$
10	5.5	0.03025	6.4	0.0320	5.4	0.02592
35	16.7	0.09185	19.1	0.0955	16.0	0.0768
60	27.9	0.15345	31.6	0.1580	27.2	0.13056

It will be evident from the above experiments that p_H optimum for the enzyme action in the case of hydroquinone is in the neighbourhood of p_H 5. It should be mentioned here that hydroquinone alone suffers very little oxidation when shaken in a Barcroft vessel.

Temperature has very little effect on the enzymatic oxidation of hydroquinone, as is evident from the above tables.

TABLE II a.

Leucine.

Temp. = 25°. Strength of stock solution = 0.2%.

t.	p_H 4.494 $K=0.0057$		p_H 5.239 $K=0.0051$		p_H 6.2 $K=0.0049$	
	$P_d.$	$V_o.$	$P_d.$	$V_o.$	$P_d.$	$V_o.$
10	2.9	0.01653	4.5	0.02295	3.2	0.01568
35	5.5	0.03135	7.8	0.03978	6.0	0.0294
60	6.5	0.03605	9.0	0.0459	7.0	0.0343
90	8.5	0.04845	10.1	0.05151	9.0	0.0441

TABLE IIb.

Temp. = 34.4°.

t.	p_H 4.49 $K=0.0055$		p_H 5.2 $K=0.005$		p_H 6.2 $K=0.0048$		p_H 6.8 $K=0.0055$	
	$P_d.$	$V_o.$	$P_d.$	$V_o.$	$P_d.$	$V_o.$	$P_d.$	$V_o.$
10	3.4	0.0187	3.8	0.0190	4.8	0.02304	3.2	0.01760
35	5.6	0.0308	6.2	0.0312	5.9	0.02832	4.9	0.02695
73	7.6	0.0418	8.4	0.0420	8.2	0.03936	7.5	0.04126
120	9.0	0.0495	10	0.0500	10.3	0.04944	9.0	0.64950

In this case also the optimum p_H equals to 5.2.

TABLE IIIa.

Succinic acid.

Temp. = 25°. Stock solution = 1% soln.

t.	p_H 4.49 $K=0.0057$		p_H 5.2 $K=0.0051$		p_H 6.2 $K=0.0049$	
	$P_d.$	$V_o.$	$P_d.$	$V_o.$	$P_d.$	$V_o.$
10	1.7	0.00969	3.3	0.01683	2.7	0.01323
35	3.7	0.02109	5.8	0.02958	6.0	0.0294
60	4.9	0.02793	8.4	0.04284	7.0	0.0343
120	6.6	0.03762	10.0	0.05100	8.3	0.04067

 TABLE IIIb₂

Temp. = 34°.

t.	p_H 4.49 $K=0.0055$		p_H 5.2 $K=0.005$		p_H 6.2 $K=0.0048$		p_H 6.8 $K=0.0055$	
	$P_d.$	$V_o.$	$P_d.$	$V_o.$	$P_d.$	$V_o.$	$P_d.$	$V_o.$
10	3.3	0.01815	4.9	0.0245	5.3	0.02544	2.7	0.01485
35	6.5	0.03575	8.7	0.0435	8.2	0.03936	5.8	0.03190
60	8.0	0.0440	10.1	0.0505	10.0	0.0480	7.8	0.0429

p_H 5.2 is again the optimum point.

TABLE IV a.

*Acetaldehyde.*Temp. = 25°. Strength of stock solution = $M/2$.

<i>t.</i>	$p_H 4.49$ $K = 0.00557$		$p_H 5.2$ $K = 0.0057$		$p_H 6.2$ $K = 0.0057$	
	<i>Pd.</i>	<i>Vo.</i>	<i>Pd.</i>	<i>Vo.</i>	<i>Pd.</i>	<i>Vo.</i>
10	6.1	0.03477	7.0	0.0357	7.2	0.04104
35	7.5	0.04275	9.0	0.0459	10.0	0.057
60	8.0	0.0456	9.4	0.04794	10.2	0.05814
120	9.8	0.05586	11.0	0.0561	11.6	0.06612

TABLE IV b.

Temp. = 34.4°.

<i>t.</i>	$p_H 4.49$ $K = 0.0055$		$p_H 5.2$ $K = 0.0048$		$p_H 6.2$ $K = 0.0055$	
	<i>Pd.</i>	<i>Vo.</i>	<i>Pd.</i>	<i>Vo.</i>	<i>Pd.</i>	<i>Vo.</i>
10	9.0	0.0495	10	0.048	9.7	0.05335
35	10.2	0.0561	12	0.0576	11.1	0.06105
60	10.9	0.05995	12.6	0.06048	11.9	0.06545
90	11.4	0.06270	12.8	0.06124	12.6	0.06930

The optimum p_H is 6.2 and there is an appreciable temperature coefficient.

Linoleic and oleic acids.—It was found that these two acids dissolved in a solution of sodium taurocholate and sodium chloride. Presence of lecithin slightly increased the solubility of these two acids. Blank experiments showed that neither taurocholate nor lecithin was oxidised either alone or in presence of betel juice. Experiments were done with and without lecithin. Lecithin had a slight accelerating effect on the oxidation of linoleic acid in presence of betel juice but a retarding effect on the oxidation of oleic acid.

TABLE V a.

Linoleic acid.

Temp. = 25°. Stock solution = 1 c.c. linoleic acid in 100 c.c. soln. containing 5g. Na-taurocholate and 1g. NaCl.

t.	p_H 4.49 $K = 0.0057$		p_H 5.2 $K = 0.0051$		p_H 6.2 $K = 0.0049$	
	Pd.	V _o .	Pd.	V _o .	Pd.	V _o .
10	3.7	0.02109	5.0	0.0255	4.0	0.0196
35	5.9	0.03363	7.4	0.03774	6.2	0.03033
60	7.3	0.04161	9.6	0.04896	8.0	0.0392
90	9.0	0.0513	11.2	0.05712	10	0.0490

TABLE V b₂

Temp. = 34.4°.

t.	p_H 4.49 $K = 0.0055$		p_H 5.2 $K = 0.005$		p_H 6.2 $K = 0.0048$		p_H 6.8 $K = 0.0055$	
	Pd.	V _o .	Pd.	V _o .	Pd.	V _o .	Pd.	V _o .
10	2.4	0.01326	3.0	0.015	3.3	0.01584	1.4	0.0077
35	4.5	0.02475	5.5	0.0275	5.9	0.02832	3.6	0.01910
60	5.6	0.03089	7.0	0.0350	7.4	0.03552	4.5	0.02475
120	7.6	0.04180	9.5	0.0475	10.0	0.0480	6.0	0.0330

TABLE VI.

Linoleic acid with lecithin.

Stock solution same as in Table Va but contains a trace of lecithin.

Temp. = 34.4°.

t.	p_H 4.49 $K = 0.0055$		p_H 5.2 $K = 0.0048$		p_H 6.2 $K = 0.0055$	
	Pd.	V _o .	Pd.	V _o .	Pd.	V _o .
13	3.0	0.0165	4.2	0.02016	4.1	0.02255
35	6.5	0.03575	7.1	0.03408	7.0	0.0385
60	8.9	0.04895	9.0	0.0432	8.6	0.04730
90	10.2	0.05610	10.1	0.04848	9.7	0.05335

TABLE VII a.

Oleic acid.

Stock solution 1 c.c. dissolved in 100 c.c. solution of 5 g. Na-taurocholate and 0.9 g. NaCl. Temp. = 25°.

t.	p_H 4.49 $K=0.0057$		p_H 5.2 $K=0.0051$		p_H 6.2 $K=0.0049$	
	$P_d.$	$V_o.$	$P_d.$	$V_o.$	$P_d.$	$V_o.$
10	4.0	0.0228	4.6	0.02344	4.5	0.02205
35	5.7	0.03249	6.4	0.03263	6.3	0.03087
60	6.0	0.0342	6.8	0.03468	6.7	0.03283
120	7.2	0.04104	8.6	0.04437	8.0	0.0384

TABLE VIIb.

Temp. = 34.4°.

t.	p_H 4.49 $K=0.0055$		p_H 5.2 $K=0.005$		p_H 6.2 $K=0.0048$	
	$P_d.$	$V_o.$	$P_d.$	$V_o.$	$P_d.$	$V_o.$
10	5.4	0.02970	5.7	0.0285	5.3	0.02544
35	9.6	0.05180	10.7	0.0535	10.0	0.04800
60	11.0	0.06050	12.7	0.0635	12.4	0.05952

TABLE VIII.

Oleic acid with lecithin.

Stock solution same as in Table VIIa but contains a trace of lecithin. Temp. = 34.4°.

t.	p_H 4.49 $K=0.0055$		p_H 5.2 $K=0.005$		p_H 6.2 $K=0.0046$	
	$P_d.$	$V_o.$	$P_d.$	$V_o.$	$P_d.$	V_{O_2}
10	1.3	0.00715	1.5	0.0075	1.2	0.00576
35	3.8	0.01930	4.2	0.0210	3.9	0.01872
60	5.5	0.03025	6.2	0.0310	5.9	0.02832
120	8.0	0.0440	8.9	0.0445	9.3	0.04467

Effect of potassium cyanide on the oxidation.—Effect of potassium cyanide, brought upto the desired p_H on the

oxidation of hydroquinone and acetaldehyde in presence of betel juice was also tried. In both cases a retardation was obtained but the reaction did not completely stop. In the case of hydroquinone a 75% retardation was obtained. In the case of acetaldehyde oxidation as the hydrocyanic acid concentration varied from $M/360$ to $M/1440$ the retardation varied from 45% to 20%. Thus the retardation by hydrocyanic acid is of a much lower order than that expected on Warburg's hypothesis.

In the case of acetaldehyde the effect of changing its concentration keeping that of hydrocyanic acid constant was also tried. It was found that with the increased concentration of acetaldehyde the retardation by hydrocyanic acid decreased. This can be explained by assuming that the aldehyde cyanhydrin has got no retarding effect and as the concentration of the acetaldehyde increases that of the cyanhydrin also increases. Similar results were obtained by Wieland and Bertho in their experiments on the effect of hydrocyanic acid on acetic acid fermentation (*Annalen*, 1928, 467, 95). The following tables indicate the results:

TABLE IX.

Effect of KCN on hydroquinone.

Temp. = 34°. Each vessel contains 10 c.c. of 2% hydroquinone, 5 c.c. betel leaf juice, 2 c.c. buffer, 1 c.c. $M/500$ -KCN or water.

Time.	KCN.	Pressure diff.	p_{H} .	K .	O ₂ absorbed.
10 min.	absent	16.3 cm.	4.49	0.005	0.0815 c.c.
20		31.0			0.1550
60		31.5			0.1575
10	present	3.9	4.49	0.0048	0.001872
20		7.6			0.03648
60		9.2			0.04462
10	absent	12	6.2	0.0061	0.0732
20		21.4			0.13054
60		24.5			0.14945
10	present	4.2	6.2	0.0051	0.02142
20		7.9			0.04029
60		9.1			0.04641

TABLE X.

Effect of KCN on acetaldehyde.

Concentration of acetaldehyde was kept constant while that of KCN was changed. Each vessel contained 10 c.c. of *M*/2-acetaldehyde, 5 c.c. betel juice, 2 c.c. buffer, and 1 c.c. KCN soln. Temp. = 34°. p_H 6.2.

<i>t.</i>	<i>K</i> = 0.005 <i>M</i> /360-KCN		<i>K</i> = 0.0448 <i>M</i> //720-KCN		<i>K</i> = 0.006 <i>M</i> /1440-KCN		<i>K</i> = 0.0051 KCN-nil.	
	<i>P</i> _{d.}	<i>V</i> _{o.}	<i>P</i> _{d.}	<i>V</i> _{o.}	<i>P</i> _{d.}	<i>V</i> _{o.}	<i>P</i> _{o.}	<i>V</i> _{o.}
10	6.9	0.0345	7.5	0.036	8.6	0.0516	13.5	0.06885
35	9.5	0.0475	10.1	0.04848	10.7	0.0642	15.7	0.08007
60	10.1	0.0505	11.0	0.05280	11.2	0.0666	16.6	0.08466
120	11.1	0.0555	13.0	0.0624	11.5	0.0690	17.0	0.0867

TABLE XI.

Effect of KCN on acetaldehyde.

Concentration of acetaldehyde was varied while that of KCN kept constant. Each vessel contained 10. c.c. of acetaldehyde of requisite strength, 5 c.c. betel juice, 2 c.c. buffer, 1 c.c. *M*/20-KCN. Temp. = 34°. p_H 6.2.

<i>t.</i>	<i>K</i> = 0.005 <i>M</i> /72-aldehyde		<i>K</i> = 0.0048 <i>M</i> /36-aldehyde		<i>K</i> = 0.006 <i>M</i> /18-aldehyde		<i>K</i> = 0.0051 <i>M</i> /18-aldehyde without KCN.	
	<i>P</i> _{d.}	<i>V</i> _{o.}	<i>P</i> _{d.}	<i>V</i> _{o.}	<i>P</i> _{d.}	<i>V</i> _{o.}	<i>P</i> _{d.}	<i>V</i> _{o.}
10	4.4	0.022	5.1	0.02448	5.5	0.033	10.0	0.051
20	5.0	0.025	6.0	0.0288	6.1	0.0366	10.6	0.05406
40	6.1	0.0305	7.3	0.03504	7.3	0.0438	12.1	0.06171
60	6.7	0.0335	8.0	0.0384	7.5	0.045	12.4	0.06324
120	8.9	0.0445	9.8	0.04704	8.1	0.0522	14.4	0.07344

On the catalase present in betel juice.—Some experiments were carried out to determine the catalase present in the betel juice. For this purpose the juice prepared, clarified and brought to the desired p_H as in the previous experiments, was employed. An acetate buffer

of p_H 5.3 was used. Each Barcroft vessel contained 10 c.c. of $M/40$ hydrogen peroxide solution at p_H 5.3, 5 c.c. of betel juice at p_H 5.3, 2 c.c. of acetate buffer and 1 c.c. of water brought to p_H 5.3. The catalase decomposed H_2O_2 liberating oxygen and that caused an increase in pressure which was noted. Table XII shows the results.

TABLE XII.

Temp. = 34.4°.

Time.	Pressure diff.	p_H .	K .	O_2 liberated.
10 mins.	17 cm.	5.3	0.0051	0.0867 c.c.
35	28			0.1428
60	37			0.1887
80	46			0.2346

Effect of hydrocyanic acid on betel juice catalase was also tried. Along with the above mentioned experiment three other experiments were simultaneously carried out in which 1 c.c. of water was replaced by 1 c.c. of KCN of different strength, but all brought up to p_H 5.3. The results in Table XIII show considerable retardation of catalase action.

TABLE XIII.

Effect of hydrocyanic acid on catalase.

Each vessel contains 10. c.c. of $M/40-H_2O_2$, 5 c.c. of betel leaf juice, 2 c.c. of acetate buffer, 1 c.c. of KCN. Temp. = 34.4°.

Time.	Conc. of KCN.	Pressure diff.	p_H .	K .	O_2 liberated.
10 min.	$M/360$	5.5 cm.	5.3	0.005	0.02725 c.c.
35		5.5			0.055
60		14.6			0.073
120		20.8			0.104
10	$M/720$	6.3	5.3	0.0048	0.03024
35		12.1			0.05808
60		16.0			0.0768
120		21.2			0.10176
10	$M/1440$	7.2	5.3	0.0059	0.04248
35		14.3			0.08437
60		14.8			0.10502
120		22.0			0.1298

DISCUSSION.

It is clear from the above experiments that betel juice is capable of bringing about the oxidation of many substances. It is scarcely possible that a single enzyme is active in all cases ; a difference in p_H optimum also points to that.

As regards the mechanism of oxidation Warburg's theory alone is scarcely sufficient to explain all the observations. Hydrocyanic acid does not completely inhibit the oxidation. On the other hand the inhibition of oxidation by hydrocyanic acid appears to be of the same order as the inhibitions of catalase action by hydrocyanic acid. This lends strong support to the views of Wieland according to whom hydrogen peroxide is the primary product of all biological oxidations in oxygen which is at once decomposed by the catalase present.

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